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ABSTRACT

The growing demand for monitoring and detecting biochemical changes is driving the development of scalable, easy-to-fabricate, and low-power consuming sensor technologies. In particular, chemiresistors are simple and cost-effective platforms that transduce chemical interactions into measurable electrical signals. Due to the large high surface-to-volume ratio, ultrathin metal films (UTMFs) have the potential for highly sensitive transducing materials. In this study, we investigate the suitability of gold (Au) UTMFs as chemiresistive transducing material by quantifying how film thickness influences their resistive response. As a prototypical detection target, we use self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) that can be easily functionalized on the Au UTMF surface. Real-time resistance measurements during SAM formation demonstrate that the thinner the Au UTMFs, the higher the sensitivity and the faster the response. In addition, we present a proof-of-concept biosensor using SH-PEG-Biotin SAMs for the detection of streptavidin, comparing the responses between shorter and longer PEG chains. The results show that shorter PEG chains forming SAMs provide greater sensitivity and a lower limit of detection. These results highlight the potential use of Au UTMF-based chemiresistors with SAMs as scalable and tunable biosensing platforms, where sensitivity and performance can be tailored via surface molecular engineering.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The ability to monitor and detect real-time chemical and biological changes is key to modern healthcare, environmental safety, and industrial process control.¹ From wearable devices that track physiological parameters to environmental sensors monitoring air or water quality, sensing technologies are being developed to meet the increasing demand for fast, reliable, and selective detection technologies. In particular, there is a scientific interest in faster transduction mechanisms compatible with scalable sensors, minimal power requirements, and straightforward fabrication.²

Chemiresistors are a class of electrochemical sensing devices that convert chemical interactions between their surface and the target molecules into a measurable change in electrical resistance.^{3,4} Their simplicity, low-cost fabrication, and compatibility with

scalable integration make them appealing for point-of-care diagnostics, portable monitoring, and wearable devices. Their operational principle relies on a receptor element, which interacts with the target analyte, and a transducer mechanism, which converts those interactions into changes in the electrical properties. Traditional metal-oxide chemiresistors, such as SnO₂ or ZnO, rely on redox processes involving surface-absorbed oxygen species, which modulate the free-carrier concentration of the metal-oxide material.^{5,6} Conductive polymer chemiresistors typically respond through charge doping processes or changes in the polymer chain conformation.⁷ Metal-based chemiresistors operate through chemisorption or specific molecular attachment, which modifies the electron scattering at the surface and grain boundaries, thereby altering the film's resistivity.^{8–10} The specific use and tailoring of the receptor and transducing sensing material can determine the type of analyte that

can be detected, such as gases,^{8,11} ions,^{12–14} and biomolecules.^{15–17} In metal-based platforms, however, achieving selective molecular detection often requires specific surface functionalization. To further optimize the selectivity and sensitivity of metal-based sensing devices, self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) can be grown for specific functionalization and target detection.^{15,17–19}

SAMs are ordered molecular layers formed through the specific adsorption and/or covalent grafting of molecules onto solid surfaces. Molecules forming SAMs generally consist of long chains, which can be divided into three parts: a head group that anchors to the substrate via covalent bonding or strong specific interaction, a tail group that acts as a spacer, and often a functional group that can be engineered to interact selectively with the target analyte. In particular, sulfur-based head groups such as thiols (–SH) have gained particular relevance due to their specific binding with gold (Au) surfaces, as Au is one of the most widely used materials in biosensor technologies.^{20–22} The adsorption kinetics, surface coverage, and structural conformation of SAMs have been extensively described by Langmuir-type models, providing a highly reproducible and chemically controlled system for probing the sensitivity and transduction properties of novel materials for sensing applications.^{23–25} Indeed, SAMs have been extensively used to investigate the electron transport and surface electron scattering phenomena in metallic films.⁹ Moreover, SAM formation enables precise control over the physicochemical properties of the sensing interface, thereby enhancing selective molecular recognition and boosting the potential for biosensing applications.²⁶

Recent advances in nanofabrication have enabled the creation of continuous ultrathin metal films (UTMFs), which are metal films with thicknesses lower than 10 nm and electrically conductive below their standard percolation threshold.^{27,28} Due to their extremely low thickness, these films exhibit an enhanced surface-to-volume ratio, making them highly responsive to any change in their surface attributes. In the case of electrical properties, surface interactions modulate the carrier density and scattering mechanisms within the ultra-thin films, inducing changes in their optical and electrical properties.^{9,10,28,29} However, the transduction sensitivity of Au UTMFs upon the interaction of molecular species

and the dependence on the film thickness have not been explored yet. In particular, the development of Au UTMFs offers new opportunities for their application in biochemical sensors such as chemiresistors.

In this study, we evaluate the sensitivity of Au UTMFs as chemiresistor sensing material with the functionalization of thiol-based SAMs as a controlled molecular analyte. First, we explore the real-time formation of SAMs on Au UTMFs using SH-PEG-COOH molecules through the electrical response of the system and atomic force microscopy (AFM) measurements. To further prove the SAM formation, we modeled the electrical response of the system based on Mayadas–Shatzkes (MS) and Fuchs–Sondheimer (FS) models and performed X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS). We also fit the electrical measurements with molecular adsorption dynamics given by a Langmuir-based kinetic model. Second, we present a proof-of-concept chemiresistor biosensor based on Au UTMF and functionalized with SH-PEG-Biotin SAM for the detection of different streptavidin concentrations, demonstrating the platform's applicability for detecting biological analytes.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Sensor design and operation principles

The proposed chemiresistive sensor platform is shown in Fig. 1. The system is based on cupric oxide (CuO)-seeded Au UTMFs with thick titanium (Ti)/Au metal contacts patterned onto silicon/silica (Si/SiO₂) substrates. Figure 1(a) shows the sensor connected to the electrical measurement system alongside a sealed liquid cell, which contains the liquid analyte and enables extended measurement durations. The zoom inset in Fig. 1(a) shows a microscope image of the sensor's exposed area where the Au UTMF is in direct contact with the liquid analyte. Figure 1(b) illustrates the cross section of the device, and Fig. 1(c) provides a close-up view of the sensing region, providing a molecular-level view of the sensor's working principle, highlighting the SAM formation and the changes in the Au free-carrier behavior.

When thiol-functionalized molecules interact with the Au surface, the sulfur atoms form strong covalent bonds with the Au atoms

FIG. 1. Chemiresistive sensor platform based on Au UTMF and thiol-based SAM: (a) photograph of the sensor, liquid cell, and connections to the electrical electrodes (left), and a microscope image of the sensor's active material area composed of Au UTMF (right); (b) schematic representation of the chemiresistive sensor and liquid cell connected to the resistance measuring system; and (c) close-up view of the active area shown in (b), illustrating the bonding between the thiol groups of the SH-PEG-COOH molecules and the Au atoms in the UTMF, the interaction between free electrons in the Au UTMF and the new surface scattering centers, and the different sensor layers.

(S–Au bonding).²¹ From the sensor's perspective, these molecular interactions lead to a reduction in the free carrier density and an increase in electron scattering within the Au UTMF.^{9,10} Several models based on Mayadas and Shatzkes (MS) or Fuchs-Sondheimer (FS) theories have been used to model these changes in the electrical properties of metal films as a change in the electron scattering parameters.^{30,31} The adsorption of thiol molecules introduces additional surface scattering centers, effectively reducing the electron mean free path and increasing the film resistivity, in agreement with previous studies on thiol-functionalized Au films.⁹ Nevertheless, both effects result in a measurable increase in the film's electrical resistance, which can be recorded in real-time. Due to the high surface-to-volume ratio of the UTMFs, these effects are especially pronounced, allowing enhanced sensitivity.^{27,29}

Regarding the SAM formation, S–Au bonding enables the molecules to anchor to the surface, gradually covering it over time.²¹ The thickness of the SAM depends on the composition and molecular weight of the molecules involved. In our case, we used SH-PEG-[Functional group], where the functional groups are either a carboxyl group ([–COOH]) or a biotin vitamin ([–Biotin]). The term PEG refers to polyethylene glycol [H–(O–CH₂–CH₂)_n–OH], where the term “n” denotes the number of monomer units in the polymer chain. The molecular weights used are 10 kDa for the SH-PEG-COOH and 400 Da and 10 kDa for the SH-PEG-Biotin. When PEG chains are fully extended in liquid media, the estimated length is ~63.6 nm for the 10 kDa molecular weight and 2.5 nm for the 400 Da.³² However, this length can be significantly reduced to a few nanometers in dry conditions due to morphological changes in the molecules (chain collapse and close molecule interdigitation).^{33–35}

The process of SAM formation is often described using the Langmuir adsorption model, which assumes a flat, homogeneous surface with independent binding sites and no interaction between the molecules.^{21,23–25,36,37} According to this model, surface coverage evolves over time following a first-order kinetics:

$$\theta(t) = 1 - e^{-kt}, \quad (1)$$

where $\theta(t)$ represents the surface coverage at time t , and k is the adsorption rate constant. This model describes the chemisorption kinetics of the SAM formation and provides an interpretation of the time evolution of the sensor response. Observed deviations from the model at early time scales are typically attributed to physisorption, molecular reorganization, or intermolecular phenomena.^{22,23,25}

The use of SAM in biosensing applications can be engineered to selectively target the detection of a specific analyte.^{15,16} The interaction between specific functional groups and their target analytes induces conformational or electrostatic changes in the SAM layer. In chemiresistor sensors, these changes can modulate the mobility of free carriers in the active material, thus enabling real-time detection and quantification of these biomolecular interactions.

B. SAM formation on Au UTMFs

The formation of thiol-based SAMs on Au UTMFs was investigated using real-time resistance measurements. The chemiresistor

sensor was exposed to SH-PEG-COOH with 10 kDa at a 1 mg ml^{−1} concentration in Milli-Q water, and the resistance was monitored using a two-point probe (2P-Probe) setup. To distinguish between the electrical changes caused by the S–Au bonding and those due to interactions between Milli-Q and the Au, control measurements using only Milli-Q water were also performed. For all cases, the relative resistance change was calculated as

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = (100\%) \cdot \frac{R(t) - R_0}{R_0}, \quad (2)$$

where R_0 refers to the resistance readout immediately after spotting the liquid solution. To further explore the dependence on the Au UTMF thickness, measurements were performed on four different film thicknesses: 2, 3, 4, and 8 nm (see Fig. S1 in the [supplementary material](#) for AFM thickness characterization). All measurements were repeated three times.

Figure 2 summarizes the formation of SAM onto Au surfaces through electrical and surface profile measurements. Figure 2(a) shows the sensor's average $\Delta R/R_0$ over time for the different Au UTMF thicknesses upon exposure to SH-PEG-COOH solution and to Milli-Q water. Overall, thinner metal films (2–4 nm) exhibited larger and faster increases in the resistance, while thicker films (8 nm) showed smaller and slower changes. The shaded areas represent the associated standard error. The higher standard errors observed in thinner films are due to deviations in the UTMF thickness during fabrication (see Fig. S1 in the [supplementary material](#)).

The trend observed in Fig. 2(a) for the SH-PEG-COOH solution exposure shows a progressive increase in the sensor resistance until a plateau is reached. This resistance increase is attributed to the S–Au bonding at the sensor's surface, which increases electron scattering and decreases the charge carrier density in the UTMF.^{9,10} The final plateau is associated with the sensor surface coverage saturation, meaning that all the binding sites are occupied. Therefore, two distinct regimes can be identified: an initial fast regime associated with molecular adsorption onto available Au binding sites, followed by a slower regime attributed to molecular reorganization within the forming monolayer. This behavior is consistent with previous reports on thiol-based SAM formation.^{25,36,37}

In contrast, the chemiresistor interaction with only Milli-Q water results in a decrease in the resistance of the film, which may be attributed to the removal of gold oxide states [Au₂O₃ and Au(OH)₃] at the surface of the sensor. In addition, the observed relative decrease in resistance with only Milli-Q water is higher as the film gets thinner, as expected from the higher surface-to-volume ratio. These oxide states may appear during the sensor fabrication process or during their storage, depending on the conditions. It has been shown that the exposure to ambient conditions can slowly remove these oxide states, which is attributed to the ambient humidity.²⁹

To further validate the 2P-probe measurements on the chemiresistor sensors and account for possible influences from the measurement setup's intrinsic resistance, four-point probe (4P-probe) measurements of sheet resistance, R_s , were performed on large-area Au UTMFs with different thicknesses. The R_s values were taken before and after 24-h of SH-PEG-COOH solution incubation (see Table SI in the [supplementary material](#)). The relative sheet resistance changes $\Delta R_s/R_{s,0}$ are shown in Fig. 2(b), which are consistent

FIG. 2. Thiol-based SAM formation on chemiresistive sensors based on Au UTMFs. (a) Relative resistance ($\Delta R/R_0$) temporal evolution of chemiresistive sensors with different Au UTMFs thicknesses. The results show the cases of SH-PEG-COOH solution in Milli-Q water and pure Milli-Q as a control. Each Au UTMF thickness is represented by a different color: 2 nm (dark gray), 3 nm (red), 4 nm (blue), and 8 nm (green). Thick dark lines represent the average of three independent measurements, and the shaded regions represent the corresponding standard deviation. (b) Relative sheet resistance changes ($\Delta R_s/R_{s,0}$) on Au UTMFs films with different thicknesses after 24-h incubation in SH-PEG-COOH solution. The same colors are coded as in (a). (c) AFM height profile of a $10\ \mu\text{m}$ wide ribbon made of a 50 nm Au film with a 0.5 nm CuO seed layer, before (light gray) and after (cyan) 24-h incubation in SH-PEG-COOH solution. Measurement in dry conditions.

with the results obtained using the 2P-probe configuration shown in Fig. 2(a).

In addition, Fig. 2(c) shows the AFM height profiles of a thick metal ribbon (50 nm Au with a 0.5 nm CuO seed layer, $10\ \mu\text{m}$ wide) before (light gray) and after (cyan) 24-h of SH-PEG-COOH solution incubation. Since the AFM measurements were performed in dry conditions, only a $\sim 3.5\ \text{nm}$ increase in thickness was observed after incubation. This increase aligns with expected SAM dimensions considering partial molecular folding and compression during drying.^{32–34}

In addition, to extend the influence of film thickness on the electrical response, additional sheet resistance measurements were performed on Au UTMFs with thicknesses ranging from 2 to 32 nm, both before and after SAM incubation (see the [supplementary material](#), Sec. S3). In addition, AFM analyses were carried out to extract the surface roughness and its lateral scale, used here as an estimate of the effective grain size. These parameters were incorporated into an electrical conductivity model based on electron scattering mechanisms adapted from Refs. 30 and 31. The modeled results further indicate that the increase in the film resistance upon SAM formation arises from an increase in surface electron scattering.

To further confirm the chemical nature of the SAM formation, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were performed (see Fig. S4 in the [supplementary material](#)). The results after the SAM incubation show the characteristic S(2p) doublet associated with Au–S bonding, in agreement with literature reports, confirming the formation of thiolated standing up configuration SAMs.³⁸

Overall, these observations confirm the SAM formation on the Au UTMF surface and highlight the thickness-dependent sensitivity of the chemiresistor platform.

C. Langmuir adsorption kinetics

Figure 3 shows the fitting of the experimental resistance changes of the thiol-based SAM formation with SH-PEG-COOH on the chemiresistors with Au UTMFs, using the Langmuir adsorption model. The continuous lines in Fig. 3(a) represent the average $\Delta R/R_0$ over time [previously shown in Fig. 2(a), without the shaded error], while the dashed lines correspond to the fitted Langmuir curves. The inset in Fig. 3(a) shows the initial 3 h of each measurement, highlighting the initial resistance drop in the sensor caused by the initial interaction with the Milli-Q water. As the SH-PEG-COOH molecules begin to bond onto the Au surface and the SAM starts forming, the resistance increases. Therefore, the Langmuir fit was applied starting only after the resistance minimum was reached. To model the kinetics of the SAM formation in our specific case, Eq. (1) was modified as

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \left[\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} \right]_{\min} + \left[\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} \right]_{\max} \left[1 - e^{-k(t-t_0)} \right], \quad (3)$$

where $[\Delta R/R_0]_{\min}$ is the resistance minimum due to the initial dip from the Milli-Q interaction, t_0 is the time when the SH-PEG-COOH interaction begins to dominate the surface interaction, and $[\Delta R/R_0]_{\max}$ is the saturated SAM signal. R_0 remains as the resistance readout immediately after the liquid solution deposition. Table SIII in the [supplementary material](#) summarizes the fitting parameters.

Figure 3(b) shows the extracted model parameters of the Langmuir model: the saturation signal $[\Delta R/R_0]_{\min} + [\Delta R/R_0]_{\max}$ (top plot) and the adsorption rate constant k (bottom plot), both represented against the Au UTMF thickness. For the saturation signal, an exponential decay trend is observed, indicating that thinner

FIG. 3. Langmuir fitting for the thiol-based SAM formation on chemiresistive sensors: (a) relative resistance temporal evolution of chemiresistive sensors with different Au UTMFs thicknesses. SH-PEG-COOH SAM formation (solid lines) and corresponding Langmuir fitting (dashed lines). Each Au UTMF thickness is represented with a different color: 2 nm (dark gray), 3 nm (red), 4 nm (blue), and 8 nm (green). The inset shows the first 3 h of the sensor response and SAM formation. Langmuir fitting starts at the minimum resistance point. (b) Maximum sensor saturation signal values obtained from the Langmuir fitting (colored markers) for each Au UTMF thickness, along with an exponential decay fit of the data (dashed black line). (c) Adsorption rate constants obtained from the Langmuir fitting (colored markers) for each Au UTMF thickness, along with a linear fit of the data (dashed black line). Both (b) and (c) markers use the same colors as in (a).

UTMFs exhibit higher resistance changes, thus confirming their enhanced surface sensitivity. In contrast, the adsorption rate constant decreases approximately linearly with increasing UTMF thickness, indicating that thinner films also respond more rapidly to the molecular adsorption. We believe that the faster kinetics for the thinner films may be associated with the different surface morphology, as the surface-to-volume ratio increases as the thickness of the Au UTMF decreases.^{27,28}

While the Langmuir model provides a good approximation of the overall kinetics, it assumes a single-step adsorption process onto the independent binding sites on the Au film. However, SAM formation on Au can be understood as a multi-step process. Initially, molecules rapidly adsorb onto the surface, leading to a quick increase in surface coverage.²¹ This is followed by a slower reorganization phase, where molecules rearrange into a more ordered and densely packed configuration, driven by intermolecular interactions and tail alignment. The deviations observed at shorter time scales (see Fig. S5 in the [supplementary material](#)) can therefore be attributed to this transition between step processes.²⁵

Overall, the results in Fig. 3 support that the SAM growth in our experiments follows the Langmuir model with high accuracy, particularly at larger time scales (see Fig. S5 in the [supplementary material](#)). At shorter time scales, the differences between the experimental data and the fitting increase, likely due to the coexistence of adsorption and subsequent molecular ordering processes, which are not captured by the ideal Langmuir dynamics.^{21,25} Despite these limitations, the model confirms that chemiresistors based on Au UTMF can detect the formation of thiol-based SAM and that the UTMF thickness is a critical parameter that influences both sensitivity and response speed of the sensor.

D. Proof-of-concept biosensing with SH-PEG-Biotin SAMs

To demonstrate the applicability of the Au UTMF chemiresistor platform for biosensing, a proof-of-concept experiment was performed using SH-PEG-Biotin SAMs as specific surface functionalization and streptavidin solutions at different concentrations as the target analyte. Biotin and streptavidin binding is well known for its strong and highly specific interaction, making it an ideal system for evaluating the sensitivity and functionality of surface-functionalized sensors.^{16,39} As before, all measurements were repeated three times to ensure statistical reliability.

Chemiresistors with a 3 nm thickness Au UTMF sensing region were first functionalized with SH-PEG-Biotin SAM with two different molecular weights: 400 Da and 10 kDa (see Fig. S6 in the [supplementary material](#)). The use of two PEG chain lengths enables the investigation of how the molecular weight of the molecules influences the electrical response of the system, both in the formation of the SAM and the sensor's electrical response upon the detection of streptavidin. Different functional groups and molecular weights can affect the growth and formation of SAM, as complex functional groups such as biotin can lead to unwanted intermolecular interactions that interfere with proper SAM assembly. Several studies have pointed out the benefits of building functionalized SAM in a stepwise manner, adding different types of molecules layer by layer, to minimize the interaction between complex biological functional groups.^{17,22} AFM measurements (Fig. S7 in the [supplementary material](#)) confirmed the SAM formation, with an observed thickness increase of ~ 1.4 nm for the 400 Da SAM and ~ 1.2 nm for the 10 kDa SAM. After the biotin functionalized SAM formation, the sensors were exposed to streptavidin solutions in Milli-Q water with

FIG. 4. Resistive response of a chemiresistive sensor with 3 nm Au UTMFs and SH-PEG-Biotin SAM to different streptavidin concentrations. Two SH-PEG-Biotin molecular weights are used: 400 Da (green) and 10 kDa (purple). The Y axis shows the relative resistance change due to the streptavidin signal, with the Milli-Q background subtracted to compensate for the negative baseline signal. The X axis indicates the streptavidin concentrations in $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, including the Milli-Q-only control ($0 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, no streptavidin). The error bars represent the standard deviation. The LOD was calculated from the linear regression of the different streptavidin concentrations, using 3σ from the standard deviation baseline noise from the Milli-Q water measurements.

concentrations ranging from 10 ng mL^{-1} to $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ in one order of magnitude increments. The continued temporal resistance evolution was monitored for each concentration (Fig. S8 in the [supplementary material](#)), revealing a consistent increase in the sensor readout as streptavidin was spotted. The response of Milli-Q water was measured at the start of each experiment as a control baseline, where a slight decrease in the resistance was observed in most of the sensors used. These resistance drops were attributed to potential SAM degradation over time, especially when liquid concentrations were spotted.

Figure 4 shows the relative resistance change $\Delta R/R_0$ as a function of different streptavidin concentrations for both SAM molecular weights: 400 Da (green) and 10 kDa (purple). The averaged resistance drop associated with the Milli-Q background was subtracted to compensate for the initial SAM degradation. The results show that SAM made of shorter PEG chains (smaller molecular weights) produced stronger and more linear sensor responses than the longer ones. These results may be attributed to a reduced distance between the biorecognition event and the conductive Au layer, inducing stronger carrier mobility changes. Indeed, shorter PEG chains would likely reduce steric hindrance and allow closer proximity between the biotin and the Au UTMF surface, potentially improving signal transduction. The sensitivities and limit of detections (LODs) of both SAM cases are shown in Table I. For both scenarios, the sensitivity was extracted from the slope of a linear fit to the response data, and the LOD was calculated from the linear regression of the different streptavidin concentrations and 3σ from the standard deviation baseline noise from the Milli-Q water measurements.

These results highlight the potential use of Au UTMF-based chemiresistors with thiol-based SAMs for biosensing applications. While the current measured signals, sensitivities, and LODs are

TABLE I. Sensitivity and LOD for 3 nm Au UTMF chemiresistors using biotin functionalized SAM with different molecular weight.

Molecular weight (Da)	Sensitivity ($\% \mu\text{g}^{-1} \text{ ml}$)	LOD ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)
400	0.043 ± 0.004	0.20
10 000	0.024 ± 0.008	13.00

not enough for commercial applications, they are comparable with current literature results facing similar scenarios but with improved SAM engineering.¹⁷ Further improvements in the optimization of the SAM could lead to more reliable chemiresistor sensors.

III. METHODS

A. Substrate preparation, sensor layouts, and metal film depositions

Sensors were fabricated on $36 \times 36 \text{ mm}$, 0.5 mm thickness Si/SiO₂ wafers with 1 μm SiO₂ thickness. Substrates were ultrasonically cleaned in acetone and isopropanol (5 min each), dried with nitrogen, and treated with oxygen plasma (Tepla Plasma System 310M) at 100 W, 200 ml min^{-1} O₂ flow for 3 min for surface activation. A first UV photolithography process (MLA 150) was used to define the sensor's active material area. S1805 photoresists (Microposit) were used. After, a 0.5 nm CuO seed layer was deposited by RF sputtering (AJA Orion 8) using a CuO target in an Ar:O₂ (20:2 sccm) atmosphere at 2 mTorr and 150 W. Gold UTMFs between 2 and 8 nm thickness were deposited by thermal evaporation (Kurt J. Lesker Lab 18) at 1 \AA s^{-1} . A soft lift-off in an acetone bath was performed to remove the metal and the undeveloped photoresist. A second UV photolithography process (MLA 150) was used to define the metal contacts. Metal contacts were made of a 5 nm Ti adhesion layer and 50 nm Au, deposited by e-beam and thermal evaporation (Kurt J. Lesker Lab 18) at 1 \AA s^{-1} , respectively. A final lift-off was performed in an acetone bath with sonication.

B. Materials and reagents

SH-PEG-COOH (10 kDa) and SH-PEG-Biotin (400 Da and 10 kDa) were purchased from Nanocs and dissolved in Milli-Q water at 1 mg mL^{-1} concentrations. Streptavidin from *Streptomyces avidinii* was purchased from Sigma and dissolved in Milli-Q water at concentrations ranging from 10 ng mL^{-1} to $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. All solutions were prepared fresh prior to use.

C. Electrical characterization

2P-probe resistance measurements were performed using custom-made electrical contacts connected to a Keysight B2901A Precision Source/Measured Unit (SMU). A custom LabVIEW interface was used to apply a voltage sweep from -0.01 to 0.01 V , and current measurement was performed at $\sim 5 \text{ s}$ intervals. The resistance was extrapolated from the current/voltage ratio. 4P-probe sheet resistance measurements were performed using a linear probe configuration (Cascade Microtech C4S 44/7S 3475) connected to a Keithley 2001 Multimeter.

D. AFM measurements

AFM measurements were performed using a Park NX20 AFM system. $25 \times 25 \mu\text{m}$ profile images of $10 \mu\text{m}$ width ribbons were performed with a pixel resolution of $\sim 0.098 \mu\text{m pixel}^{-1}$ (256×256 pixels). Ribbon profiles were obtained with a line averaging of 256×128 pixels.

E. XPS measurements

XPS characterization was performed with a ULVAC-PHI PHI Genesis system with monochromatic aluminum K alpha radiation at 1486 eV.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we demonstrated a chemiresistor sensor platform based on Au UTMFs functionalized with thiol-based SAMs. Real-time resistance measurements showed that thinner Au UTMFs provide higher sensitivity and faster response during the SAM formation. The SAM formation was also checked with AFM and XPS measurements, and its growth followed Langmuir adsorption kinetics. In addition, a proof-of-concept biosensor using SH-PEG-Biotin SAMs was used for the selective detection of streptavidin, showing the dependence on the SAM's molecular weight. Shorter PEG chains resulted in a more linear signal, higher sensitivity, and lower LOD than longer PEG chains. The highest sensitivity and lower LOD achieved were $0.043\% \pm 0.004\%$ and $0.200 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, respectively. These results confirm the potential of Au UTMF chemiresistors for real-time biosensing, where the choice of surface chemistry plays a key role in sensor response. Further improvements in SAM engineering could enhance device performance and enable broader biosensing applications.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The [supplementary material](#) consists of eight sections, which are as follows: Section S1 presents the atomic force microscopy (AFM) thickness characterization of the different gold (Au) ultrathin metal films (UTMFs) used as chemiresistive sensing materials; Section S2 includes sheet resistance measurements of continuous Au UTMFs with a lateral size of $15 \times 15 \text{ nm}$, measured using a four-point probe, before and after SH-PEG-COOH self-assembled monolayer (SAM) formation; Section S3 presents the AFM and sheet resistance characterization of different Au UTMFs thicknesses ranging from 2 to 32 nm, and the model used to fit the electrical behavior; Section S4 presents the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) characterization before and after SH-PEG-COOH incubation on a Au film; Section S5 summarizes the Langmuir adsorption parameters obtained from the chemiresistive measurements, including a comparison between the experimental data and the fitted values; Section S6 compares the chemiresistive responses of SH-PEG-COOH and SH-PEG-biotin SAMs for a fixed Au UTMF thickness; Section S7 shows AFM characterization of SH-PEG-biotin SAM formation on a thick Au ribbon; Section S8 presents the temporal evolution of the electrical resistance in response to different streptavidin concentrations for a 3 nm Au UTMF chemiresistor functionalized with SH-PEG-biotin SAMs.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Javier Arrés Chillón: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Daniel Martínez-Cercos:** Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Ewelina Wajs:** Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Prantik Mazumder:** Conceptualization (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Valerio Pruneri:** Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Project administration (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – original draft (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in CORA RDR at <https://doi.org/10.34810/data2512>.

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